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EVALUATION OF THE FACTORS AFFECTING CONSTRUCTION SITE PRODUCTIVITY (A CASE STUDY OF SOME SELECTED SITES IN ABUBAKAR TAFAWA BALEWA UNIVERSITY, BAUCHI)

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Abstract

This study evaluates the factors affecting construction site productivity in some selected sites in Gubi Campus of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Bauchi State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two objectives and corresponding research questions. Relevant literatures related to the research question were reviewed. The study adopted survey research design and simple random sampling technique was employed. Fifteen (15) respondents were randomly selected from the three ongoing construction sites making a total of Forty-five (45) respondents. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire and was validated by three experts. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was found to be .775 and hence the instrument was found to be reliable. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24 was used to analyse the data that was collected. The data obtained was analysed using Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation. Through the data collected for this study, it was discovered that all the 11 factors were agreed upon as the factors affecting construction site productivity and to a high extent. Based on the findings, the result of the research should serve as contribution for future research projects or studies and also help stakeholders in Bauchi, Nigerian construction industry and others around the world to make sure such factors are avoided in construction site, so as to improve the site productivity and also the construction industry's contribution to the economy of the country.

Keywords: Evaluation, Construction Site, Productivity

Introduction

The term “productivity” expresses the relationship between outputs and inputs (Karunaratna & Siriwardana, 2018). Output and input differ from one industry to another. Also, the productivity definition varies when applied to different areas of the same industry. Labour is one of the segments of the construction industry. In order to enhance the productivity of the workers, critical factors which affect the productivity should be identified (Karunaratna & Siriwardana, 2018).

Construction is a labour-intensive industry in which the skills and experience of workers influence the cost, schedule, and quality of projects significantly (Jarkas & Bitar, 2012). The construction of buildings involves the proper execution of various tasks by many differently skilled workers. The type of construction work performed and the characteristics of the workers involved significantly impact the time required to complete a specific task. Jarkas and Bitar (2012) further stated that the root causes of inefficiency in the productivity of workers are poor communication, unskillfulness, and a shortage of

construction knowledge. As a matter of fact, supervisors often face difficulties directing job orders and workers frequently struggle to comprehend work instructions.

The significant variance in the concept and definition of construction productivity among projects and companies makes creating a comprehensive productivity measurement for construction projects difficult. Measuring worker performance by monitoring their worksite activity in real-time is typically time-consuming, costly, and error-prone. Nonetheless, taking into account time and measuring production over time makes it easier to compare productivity and determine its rise or decline.

The Nigerian construction industry is be-devilled with issues ranging from corruption during the award of contracts, to the total neglect of projects due to cash flow problems. As a result, construction workers have been subjected to a work environment which does not encourage high levels of efficiency (Adagba, Ati & Ibrahim, 2021). At low levels, Construction Labour Productivity can be dangerous causing social conflicts to a Nation's economy (Shoar & Banaitis, 2019), (Palikhe, Kim, & Kim, 2018). Identification of these factors affecting productivity levels is important, as it will aid site handlers in tackling such problems thereby reducing time and cost overruns Palikhe et al (2018), Seddeeq, Assaf, Abdallah, and Hassanain, (2019). It will also help to improve labour productivity at the sites. The construction industry's productivity is vital considering the enormous effect it has on a Nation's GDP (Hafez, Aziz, Morgan, Abdullah, & Ahmed, 2018). An improved productivity means a rise in GDP.

According to Shittu and Shehu (2010), the construction industry plays an important part in the Nigeria's economic and social needs and funds substantially to national goals. According to a report by tribuneonlineng.com, 2022, the construction sector contributed 9.5 per cent to the nominal GDP in the third quarter of 2022, indicating larger investment in both residential and non-residential buildings and other construction sectors. In Nigeria construction industry employs a very high number of workers compared to other industries.

There are productivity losses in some construction sites due to the non-value adding activities happening at the site as this affects sustainable building (Hafez, et al 2014). Non-value adding activities can be defined as activities that consume time, resources or space but it does not add any value to the project. These non-value activities reduce the workers' productivity because it reduces the final output (Hafez, et al 2014). Therefore, in order to enhance the worker productivity, they have to be minimized. In this study conducted, authors have categorized the factors affecting worker productivity into management, site and resource management, project characteristics, workforce characteristics and external characteristic factors.

Furthermore, the three most important needs of human being are food, clothes and most importantly shelter; that is why construction industry becomes important to country's economy across the globe. Construction industry is one of the biggest and largest industries in Nigeria, the industry employs good number of Nigerian population and contributes 3.22% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth in Nigeria in the year 2011 (Corporate Nigeria, 2014). Even though the construction industry is important in the economy of Nigeria, the economic downfall or recession and the constantly changing of leaders in Nigeria has affected the sector where public projects are often left uncompleted or delivered to a poor quality (World Bank, 2004) as cited in Adagba, Ati & Ibrahim, 2021. Such encounter lead to the termination of ongoing projects or delay to ongoing projects. Such factors are those that affects the productivity in construction industry in a way that labor market sees an unfair wage, negative influencing factors, lack of motivation, lack of training and poor communication etc.

the extent of these failures varies within and across countries, driving national and global inequalities (Adagba, Ati & Ibrahim, 2021).

Construction is the way in which something is built or put together. It can also be defined as building of something, especially a large structure such as house, road or bridge (Farlex, 2014). Productivity is the measurement of the rate at which work is carried out. It is the measure of the efficiency of a person, machine, factory, system etc, in converting inputs into useful outputs (Khan, 2017). Construction productivity can be simply illustrated by an association between an input and output. Productivity is an important factor that affects the overall performance of any construction site, be it small or large project (Santosh & Apte, 2014).

Any improvement to the construction site productivity will have positive impact on the economic growth of the country. From the above statistics of Nigeria and Thailand, Construction industry's productivity is important to any country as it has an effect on the economic growth of a country whatsoever the situation of the industry, negative or positive. Looking at the factors that affects construction site productivity will help countries to acquire better economic growth in the future by working towards having an improved productivity in the construction industry.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian construction industry is be-devilled with issues ranging from corruption during the award of contracts, to the total neglect of projects due to cash flow problems thereby affecting productivity (Adagba, Ati & Ibrahim, 2021). As stated above, it is obvious that Nigeria, like many other countries: both developed and developing are faced with the challenges of under performance in the construction industry especially in terms of productivity, which can be seen as time, cost or quality. So many factors such as unsatisfied labour, market, payment, weather and quality of material among others, affects the productivity of projects in Nigerian construction sites negatively thereby leading to low productivity. Knowing such factors can help with an idea on how to avoid them which will lead to improved productivity. Although so many research works have been carried out on site productivity, there is still no one way to measure productivity as it varies from project manager to project manager, project to project, area to area and country to country. It is against this background that this study investigated the factors affecting construction site productivity and the extent to which these factors affect construction site productivity in the study area.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this research project is to determine the factors affecting construction site productivity in some selected project in Gubi Campus of ATBU Bauchi. Specifically, this study seeks to:

1. To determine the factors affecting construction site productivity.
2. To determine the extent to which these factors affect construction site productivity.

Research Question

The following research questions were raised in this study:

1. What are the factors affecting construction site productivity?
2. To what extent does these factors affect construction site productivity?

Methodology

The research design used in the study was a survey research design. The area of the study was construction sites located within Gubi Campus of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi, Bauchi State. The population of the study constitutes labour workers and foremen of the construction sites within Gubi Campus of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi. Total sample population was employed. The three ongoing construction sites were used within the area of the study. Ten labour workers and five foremen were randomly selected from each of the three construction sites, making a total of forty-five (45) respondents. The instrument for data collection for this research was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers through extensive literature review. The instrument was validated by three experts from the Department of Vocational and Technology Education (DVTE) Building Option, Faculty of Technology Education, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi, Bauchi State. The instrument was administered with the aid of three research assistants from each of the construction site. The research assistants were educated on the procedure for data collection. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data. A cut off point 2.99 and below were disagreed and any item with a mean score of 3.00 and above were accepted. The items for response were presented according to the research questions with five points Linkert scale. The ratings for research question one and two are respectively as follows:

Strongly Agreed (SA)	5	Points
Agreed (A)	4	Points
Undecided (U)	3	Points
Disagreed (D)	2	Points
Strongly Disagreed (SD)	1	Point
Very serious (VS)	5	points
Serious (S)	4	points
Undecided (U)	3	points
Least Serious (LS)	2	points
Not Serious (NS)	1	point

Results and Discussion

Research Question One: What are the factors affecting construction site productivity?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the respondents on the factors affecting construction site productivity.

S/N	Items	N	X	SD	Remark
1.	Unfair wages	45	5.00	.000	Strongly Agreed
2..	lack of motivation	45	4.51	.742	Strongly Agreed
3.	Recruitment of unskilled workers	45	4.34	.873	Agreed
4.	Poor communication	45	4.17	1.014	Agreed
5.	Poor specification	45	4.17	1.014	Agreed
6.	Lack of staff development	45	4.03	1.361	Agreed
7.	Lack of investment in research and development	45	3.83	1.071	Agreed
8.	Negative influencing factors	45	3.83	1.071	Agreed
9.	Bad weather	45	3.66	.981	Agreed
10.	Late information	45	3.51	1.095	Agreed
11.	Design changes	45	3.49	.981	Agreed

Source: Field Work, 2023

Table 1 shows the response of respondents on the factors affecting construction site productivity. This shows that; unfair wages with the mean score of 5.00, followed by lack of motivation with 4.51, recruitment of unskilled workers with 4.34, poor communication with 4.17, poor specification with 4.17, lack of staff development with 4.03, lack investment in research and development with 3.83, negative influencing factor with 3.83, bad weather with 3.66, late information with 3.51 and design changes with 3.49 being the least factor which was identified as factor affecting construction site productivity.

Research Question Two: To what extent does these factors affect construction site productivity.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent to which these factors affect construction site.

S/N	Items	N	X	SD	Remark
1.	Unfair wages	45	5.00	.000	Very Serious
2..	Lack of motivation	45	4.77	.490	Very Serious
3.	Poor communication	45	4.51	.742	Very Serious
4.	Lack of staff development	45	4.34	.873	Serious
5.	Negative influencing factor	45	4.17	1.014	Serious
6.	Poor specification	45	4.03	1.361	Serious
7.	Late information	45	3.83	1.071	Serious
8.	Out of sequence of work	45	3.66	.998	Serious
9.	Recruitment of unskilled labour	45	3.49	.981	Serious
10.	Lack of investment in research and development	45	3.40	1.459	Serious

Source: Field Work 2023

Table two shows the mean response of the respondents on the extent to which these factors affect construction site productivity. The results shows that unfair wages with 5.00 having the highest ranking, followed by lack of motivation with 4.77, Poor communication with 4.51, lack of development with 4.34, negative influencing factor with 4.17, poor specification with 4.03, late information with 3.83, out of sequence of work with 3.66, recruitment of unskilled labour with 3.49 and lack of investment in research and development with 3.40 having the least ranking factor.

Findings of the Study

Based on the results obtained the following findings were made by the researcher:

1. The factors that affect construction site productivity in the selected sites based on the findings of this research includes unfair wages, lack of motivation, recruitment of unskilled workers, poor communication, poor specification, lack of staff development, lack of investment in research and development, negative influencing factors, bad weather and lastly late information.
2. These factors were rated as seriously affecting construction site productivity in the selected site unfair wages, lack of motivation, poor communication, lack of staff development, negative influencing factors, poor specification, late information and lastly out of sequence of work.

Discussion of Findings

The finding identifies factors that affects construction site productivity in the studied construction sites based on the findings of this research includes unfair wages, lack of motivation, recruitment of unskilled workers, poor communication, poor specification, lack of staff development, lack of investment in research and development, negative influencing factors, bad weather and lastly late information. This finding is in agreement with that of Jarkas and Bitar, (2012) that stated that the root causes of inefficiency in the productivity of workers are poor communication, unskillfulness, and a shortage of construction knowledge. As a matter of fact, supervisors often face difficulties directing job orders and workers frequently struggle to comprehend work instructions.

In the same vein the second finding shows that all the items seriously affect construction site productivity which means when workers are not well-paid migration among them to sites that pays little more is possible and this seriously affects productivity. Lack of motivation also seriously affects construction site productivity as there is a correlation between worker's motivation and performance. Poor communication was rated as one of the factors that affect construction site productivity because communication is the life wire of any organization followed by lack of staff development which also seriously affects construction site productivity, negative influencing factors, poor specification, late information and lastly out of sequence of work were also factors that affects construction site productivity. This agrees with the literature review that when workers are not well paid it causes migration to sites that more.

Conclusion

In response to the identified factors affecting construction site productivity in some selected sites in Gubi campus of ATBU Bauchi, the researcher concludes that there are measures to be considered in an attempt to improve the productivity in construction site as such measurement will globally improve the country's GDP.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher recommends as follows:

1. That as a matter of urgency all construction sites should work towards elimination of these factors affecting construction sites productivity.
2. All construction sites should work on eliminating the extent to which these factors affect construction sites productivity.

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